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Solid Waste Management in Schools: Promoting Cleanliness, Sustainability and Environmental Awareness

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Introduction

With the daily presents of students, teachers and staff, schools produce significant amount of waste. Everyday teachers often remind students to be responsible in throwing their trashes. However, with all the reminders still students do not follow what is being reminded into them. Solid waste management is an issue that affects not only communities but also educational institutions such as schools. It is essential in school to implement Solid waste management not only to maintain cleanliness and hygiene but also promote sustainability and environmental awareness among students.

The Challenges of Solid Waste in Schools

Schools face unique challenges in managing solid waste effectively. It includes inadequate resources for effective waste management (Prisco, 2022), the need to raise awareness and encourage compliance with legislation among the school community (Regiane etc., 2023). Additionally, poor waste collection routines and student attitude towards waste management pose challenges in school respectively. The implementation of Solid Waste management program also requires the integration of waste management concepts into the school curriculum.

Importance of Solid Waste Management in School

Environmental education in schools plays a crucial role in preparing children and adolescents to adopt practices that protect the environment and reduce public health problems associated with improper waste disposal (Molina,2021).

Moreover, teaching students about proper waste management instills environmental values and fosters a sense of responsibility towards protecting the environment. Involving them in waste reduction, recycling and composting initiatives, schools can empower them to become environmentally conscious citizens who actively contribute to sustainable development in their communities.

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Effective Strategies for Solid Waste Management

Strategies to address the challenges of solid waste management in schools.

1. Waste Segregation: Motivate students and staff to follow the process of separating different types of waste materials for proper disposal or recycling.
2. Composting: Build a composting facility with the school premises to recycle organic waste into nutrient rich compost. It is an environmentally friendly way to recycle organic waste and create a valuable resource for gardening in school.
3. Educational Campaign: Organize an educational campaign and awareness-raising activities to promote responsible waste management practices in the school. Include topics on waste management into the curriculum, workshops, hand-on activities to students to strengthen learning.
4. Partnership and Collaboration: Ask support from local government agencies, non-governmental organization (NGOs) and community stakeholders.

Conclusions

Solid waste management in school is not only a practical necessity but also a moral imperative. Embracing these practices, schools can create a sustainable environment for learning, while also bring up an environmentally liable citizen. By education, collaboration and community engagement, we can build a better world for the next generation to come.

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